

OPTIMIZED CONTROL OF THE PHYSICAL BATTERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Today, a significant issue for many nations worldwide is a shortage of energy. Renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy, are being investigated as additional energy sources to address the aforementioned issue. The high investment cost and poor performance of solar energy, however, provide the biggest challenge. This study only addresses the power optimization problem. It is suggested that the method used to determine the solar system's maximum power point modify incremental conductance. Adapted Incremental Conductance algorithm based on Incremental Conductance conventional techniques. The Modified Incremental Conductance method, however, has several exceptional advantages since it has a voltage change (V) that is not constant but fluctuates in an ideal manner to achieve the maximum power point as soon as possible. The voltage V is greater away from the peak power point while it is zero at the peak power point. Modified incremental conductivity algorithm to find peak power point faster than traditional algorithms. With maximum power point change reducing ambient power loss at the highest powers point. This helps to optimize voltage difference value.

Keywords: Photovoltaic (PV), A resizing steps size INC, The modified voltage conductivity algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

To solve photovoltaic battery performance problems, a method is needed to get the highest power is shown by the photovoltaic system. Today, with the rapid development of power electronics and materials science, engineers have access to modern, compact power electronic systems that meet the needs of high-performance power converters. Thanks to the introduction of power electronics systems, the efficiency of photovoltaic PV cells is significantly increased, but the disadvantage of these systems is that they consume an additional amount of power. But because the cost of a photovoltaic battery system is still very high and the efficiency is still low, it cannot compete well in the electricity market and become the main source of energy.

The steady development of photovoltaic cell manufacturing techniques will make the use of this technology more widely available in practice. The application of MPPT algorithms aimed to further increase the efficiency of modules in photovoltaic cells. In this paper, an mINC algorithm based on the traditional INC algorithm with the optimal step-change voltage has shown a good result in detecting the maximum power point with strong changes in environmental conditions. school. The simulation results have shown that the mINC algorithm is more efficient than the previous old algorithms.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Photovoltaic battery model

For convenience in calculation and design, an equivalent circuit is given to replace the photovoltaic battery.

Figure 1. Equivalent photovoltaic battery circuit. The circuit comprises output current I, output voltage V, diode (D_J), leakage current resistor R_{SH} , and series resistor R_S

A mathematical equation shown in formula 2.1 shows, to prove the relationship between the output voltage and current output of the photovoltaic cell and the voltage. It is shown in figure 1 and the equivalence between current and voltage.

$$I = I_{PH} - I_S \left[e^{\frac{q}{kT_c A} (V + I R)} - 1 \right] - \frac{V + I R}{R_{sh}} \quad (2.1)$$

In there:

Figure 3. Simulation of the photovoltaic battery block.

➤ Control block

Figure 4. Simulation of control block.

➤ Inverter circuit block

Figure 5. Simulation block of inverter circuit.

➤ Measurement block

Figure 6. Measurement block simulation.

2.2. Proposed Improved INC Algorithm

At the MPP point, we can see $dP/dV = 0$, and when $dP/dV > 0$ then is the point to the left of MPP, and $dP/dV < 0$ then is the point to the right of MPP as shown in formula 2.3

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = \frac{(IV)}{dV} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} \cong I + \frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} \quad (2.3)$$

This is how we may do it: at point MPP, $dI/dV = -I/V$, lies to the left of the point MPP is $dI/dV > -I/V$ and lies to the right of the point MPP are $dI/dV < -I/V$. Combined with the dP/dV curve as shown in Figure 7 and figure 8, we can establish an improved INC algorithm as shown in figure 9.

Figure 7. Slope (dP/dV) of Photovoltaic battery.

Figure 8. dP/dV. Characteristic.

The improved INC algorithm flowchart was established, Based on the algorithm flowchart, we programmed the MPPT block as follows:

function

```
[Pnew,Vref,step,dPV]=do_mppt(Vnew,Inew,Vold,Iold)% Intinial iteration
```

```
N=1;
```

```
dV=Vnew-Vold;
```

```
dI=Inew-Iold;
```

```
Pnew=Vnew*Inew;
```

```
dP=Vnew*Inew-Vold*Iold;
```

```
step=N*abs(dP/dV);
```

```
dPV = dP/dV;
```

```
if step<=0.1
```

```
    step=0.1;
```

```
elseif step>=20
```

```
    step=20;
```

```
end
```

```
if dV=0
```

```
    if dI==0
```

```
        Vref=Vold;
```

```
    elseif dI>0
```

```
        Vref=Vold+step;
```

```
    else
```

```
        Vref=Vold-step;
```

```
    end
```

```
else
```

```
    if dI/dV== -Inew/Vnew
```

```
        Vref=Vold;
```

```
    elseif dI/dV> -Inew/Vnew
```

```
        Vref=Vold+step;
```

```
    else
```

```
        Vref=Vold-step;
```

```
    end
```

```
end
```

```
end
```


Figure 9. Improved INC Algorithm Flowchart.

3. RESULTS

The graph of solar radiation used in the simulation is described in fig 10.

Figure 10. The graph shows the change in solar radiation.

Figure 10 shows that the change of solar irradiance with time leads to voltage increase and decrease as shown in figure 11, which shows that solar distance affects

voltage change leading to efficiency rate will decrease in 0.2-0.3s.

Figure 11. Graph V_{pv} .

Figure 12. Graph showing the photovoltaic battery output power.

From Figures 10, figure 11, and figure 12. We see that when solar radiation changes, V_{pv} changes accordingly.

Figure 13. Graph showing the photovoltaic battery output current.

The voltage V_{pv} changes is decided by the MPPT controller and V_{pv} always ensures that $V_{pv} = V_{mpp}$, at radiation 1 (kW/m²) the value of active power pumped into the grid reaches 4593 (W) and $V_{mpp} = 676$ (V), at radiation 0.4 (kW/m²), the value of active power pumped into the grid reaches 1697 (W) and $V_{mpp} = 628$ (V), at radiation 0.8 (kW) /m²) the value of active power pumped into the grid

reached 3598 (W) and $V_{mpp} = 663$ (V). The response of the system is relatively fast within 2 cycles at the time the radiation changes ($t = 2s$ and $t = 3s$) as shown in figure (11~14).

From the graph of the output current of the photovoltaic battery as shown in figure 14. We have the corresponding pump current to the grid through the inverter.

Figure 14. Graph of current pumped into the grid through the inverter.

Figure 15. Grid voltage graph.

Figure 16. Harmonic parameters of current pumped into the grid.

From Figures 16 and figure 17. We can see that with the mINC algorithm, the current injected into the grid has low harmonic distortion (THD =

3.75%). Low grid voltage harmonic distortion (THD = 0.32%). According to the grid standard harmonic distortion should be less than 5 %.

Figure 17. Grid voltage harmonic parameters.

4. CONCLUSION

Photovoltaic battery system combining MPPT controller with advanced INC algorithm shows

good simulation results, fast response time, low harmonic distortion. In addition, the transient time of the system when there is a change in the intensity of solar radiation from the outside

environment does not exceed 2 cycles of distribution grid voltage, showing the ability to respond very quickly to the change. Constant solar radiation intensity of the external environment. An inverter with a power factor of approximately 1 pumped into the grid can be considered as a simulation system that only pumps the active power component and does not pump the reactive power component to the distribution grid.

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